

Book Review

**Book Review: *Landscapes of Investigation: Contributions to Critical Mathematics Education* (2022)
(M. G. Penteado & O. Skovsmose, Eds.)**

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For those looking for a short and to-the-point review: We highly encourage anyone involved in mathematics education or critical education to read this book (Penteado & Skovsmose, 2022), and especially those from Imperial/Colonizing nations who tend to experience less exposure to perspectives and voices from outside the Ideologically sanitized research (i.e., that which feels “safe” and “unthreatening” by virtue of reflecting dominant/oppressive norms) that comprises our status quo. This book represents the expansion of a body of research which originates primarily from places such as Brazil (Soares, 2013), influenced notably by the foundational work of Paulo Freire (e.g., 1970/2000), which explicitly eschews the sorts of Colonial/White Supremacist norms (for a list of some of these specific norms, see Brown et al., 2016) that so thoroughly pervade so much of our work and institutions. This Decolonial body of work is here built upon through international conversation and collaboration via its emergence from the Colloquium of Research in Critical Mathematics Education (Colóquio de Pesquisa em Educação Matemática Crítica). Overall, this book represents an insightful and boundary-pushing array of perspectives which we believe would serve to benefit both researchers and pedagogues interested in mathematics and critical education. Overarching topics include the following:

- Chapter 1: Introducing and contextualizing “Landscapes.”
- Chapters 2–5: Landscapes developed around economic issues, problems of racism, discussions about marijuana legalization, and issues of social justice and injustice.
- Chapters 6–10: Landscapes addressing issues of democracy, collaborative learning, global citizenship, unfinishedness, dreams, and dialogue.
- Chapters 11–14: Inclusiveness and landscapes as the meeting of differences.
- Chapters 15–18: Landscapes in university teacher education and mathematics education.

In short: Read it! The book is available Open Access, so relatively little stands in your way aside from the too-many obligations Capitalism already places upon your shoulders.

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On Lifegiving and Culturally Sustaining Research: Expanding on the Metaphor of “Landscapes” and My Experience of This Book

Above, I have attempted to offer a pragmatic and too-the-point summary of why a reader might find this book valuable and engaging. I recognize that we are all overworked and sometimes that is what people are seeking in a review. That said, I must confess that this approach to writing and expression is itself ideologically sanitized and runs contrary to how my mind (or anyone’s mind) actually works. This book is not reducible to a product—it is a physical manifestation of labor and love, an artifact brought into being through dialogue and critique. Thus, what I add here is meant to help flesh out your vision of what this book is and what you might glean in reading it, specifically by offering a much more personal account of why this book was valuable to me. As has been recognized even by nonacademic reviewers (Gastrow, 2017)², there is no way of writing a review as an objective analysis of the features and qualities of a published artifact. Instead, the value a reader derives from a review lays in understanding how and why the reviewer experienced it in a particular way. To that end, let’s talk about the central metaphor of the book and why I find it so axiologically appealing and onto-epistemically resonant.

Despite the stereotype that Autistic folk like me don’t understand metaphor, the truth is that metaphor seems to play just as fundamental a role how we learn and make sense of the world around me as it does for my Autistic peers (Rucińska et al., 2021). As I’ve phrased it elsewhere (Scheiner & Bowers, 2023, p. 10):

Far from being simple rhetorical devices, metaphors are (one of) the essential building blocks by which we make sense of our lived worlds. Much like mathematical structures, they function as cognitive isomorphisms that anchor what we come to know in what we already know. From embodied experiences of collections of objects, we abstract basic arithmetic through metaphorical mappings: equality from collections with the same number of objects, addition from pushing two or more collections together, subtraction from the act of removing a smaller collection from a larger collection (Lakoff & Núñez, 2000)... Of particular interest is that when we critically examine our metaphors of choice, we often find how our explicit and tacit knowledge of the metaphor itself can smuggle assumptions into the topic or content we are describing or navigating with that metaphor... Metaphors in and of themselves have structural assumptions that act as affordances and constraints independent of the particular characteristics painted upon them. Modifying the paint changes the surface characteristics but ultimately has no effect on the affordances and constraints imposed by the underlying metaphor.

As mentioned at the outset, this book arises out of a body of work that was explicitly pushing back on the Exercise paradigm, i.e., it is pushing back on perspectives such as the Acquisition metaphor wherein “knowledge” is something objectively measurable and individually held which is accrued through exercising the brain. Instead, the metaphor of “Landscapes” views learning as inherently complex, dialogic (collectivist), and cultural. Contrary to Sfard’s (1998) position that, in cases where two (or more) metaphors exist, what you want to do is embrace both metaphors, I instead align myself with perspectives like that of Dubbs’s (2020) who counters that treating two metaphors as “both valuable” is epistemically and ethically fraught when one of those metaphors

² Being semi-permanently meta with all of my choices including choices of citation, I’m selecting this reference in lieu of a more scholarly alternative in order to playfully tease Academics who are so caught up in internalized White Supremacy culture (Brown et al., 2016) that they still think “objectivity” is attainable despite how culturally contingent all Knowings are. All reviews are crafted where the specific work(s) and the specific observer(s) meet, so a review that describes the work but not the reviewer or their interaction is definitionally onto-epistemically flawed.

is more oppressive (not to mention more structurally misleading) than the other. I reject metaphors of exercise or acquisition as meaningful descriptions of learning broadly or mathematical exploration in particular—these metaphors impose structural constraints on how we view teaching/learning that are simultaneously oppressive and abjectly false. I find the metaphor of enculturation much more prescient, helpful, accurate, and liberatory. However, especially as a young teacher and later as a doctoral student, I struggled with how to extend this metaphor into how I analyzed mathematical tasks/explorations in of themselves. If “acquisition” invited thinking of mathematical tasks/explorations as “exercises,” then what analogue applies to the metaphor of enculturation? Here, Skovsmose (2001) eventually came to my aid: Landscapes.

Landscapes are not objects. Landscapes aren't even nouns. Landscapes are verbs: Living things, in a constant state of happening. Landscapes are dynamic and complicated and *alive*. You don't acquire a Landscape³—You interact with it, explore it, dialogue about it, live with(in) it, make art of it... You *experience* a landscape, whereas you simply *complete* an exercise. No singular exploration of a Landscape will give you complete understanding of it—even if you took the time to explore every rock, root, and raven, from every angle possible, then compiled all that into a singular image of the Landscape, you have nonetheless already failed to fully describe it—it changed while you weren't looking. For someone like me who has deep ties to a particular Landscape (Appalachia in my case), Landscapes become nigh unto spiritual, even for an agnostic like me.

I don't know if this is obvious yet or not, but these flowery descriptions I offer are not just me describing Landscapes—I am simultaneously describing what mathematics is to me. Mathematics is not some dead lifeless thing reducible to a collection of facts and procedures to be memorized and regurgitated. Instead, mathematics is a living thing, a space of beauty which is dynamic and cultural and complicated. Mathematics isn't something to be accrued and controlled, but instead something to be explored (scientifically and artistically) and experienced and enjoyed.

This book is not the only work to embrace the metaphor of Landscapes, but it is a fantastic collection of dialogically constructed work that centers this liberatory metaphor. If you, like me, feel stultified by metaphors of exercise and acquisition, this book will likely resonate with you in ways similar to (and different from) how it resonated with me. That this book is written and constructed in a way that will invite both newcomers and longstanding users of this metaphor to gain insight and push their understanding further speaks well to the care the Authors took in its construction.

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³ Despite the claims and aspirations of Capitalists.

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